

Several researches had tried to find solutions to the direct sniffing of the keyboard information. Most reasonable one of them deceives sniffing software by generating noisy data and mingling them into real keyboard information, as shown in figure 1. However, a research recently introduced a vulnerability of the keyboard controller. According to the research, a flag named C/D bit in the status register on the keyboard controller enables an attacker to steal passwords from the keyboard even the mingling algorithm is applied.[1][2]

Major difference of the USB from the PS/2 for keyboard interface is that it has a USB host controller and a root hub instead of the keyboard controller. The USB host controller is accessed through a set of registers and a memory mapped structures and buffers as shown in Fig. 2, as though some trivial differences exist between versions.

Fig. 2 USB devices are interfaced to the computer through a host controller with a set of structures that are readable and writable. The typematic information from the USB keyboard is easily sniffed by an attacker through monitoring the transaction buffers

The pHCCA is a readable and writable register containing the address of the host controller communication area that is mapped into the primary memory of the computer, in which a set of pointers to the linked lists for transaction buffers resides. Because the pHCCA register, the HCCA as well as the transaction buffers are all readable and writable for any software, the keyboard information through the USB keyboard is easily sniffed and stolen.[3]

Fig. 3 Result screen. The left one is a public interface of the authentication module for the certificate used in the Internet banking services. The right one is the client screen of the keyboard sniffing agent (device driver). The password inputted from the keyboard is acquired easily through the hardware vulnerability on both PS/2 and USB interface

III. KEYBOARD SECURITY IN HARDWARE

Security technologies are primarily involved in the field of cryptography. Because of the reason, early researches on the secure keyboard were engaged in the complex crypto issues about keyboard information.[5][6] Even though a chick cryptic technologies on the keyboard, they are not effectively applied to real input equipment because the complexity of the technologies is beyond the limit of the keyboard implementation in the points of economic feasibility or practical obstacles.

When data are transferred from one party to another, encrypted secure channel is required when a public channel is used for communication because the data could be acquired by others without permission. In the case that a secrete way could be found between allowed parties, there wouldn't be much necessary to require complex cryptography.

Hardware engineers have not been much considering how the interface in their design would be immune to tampering by software through possible vulnerability from its own; instead they focus on tamperproof of the crypto algorithms only or consider resource economy or access readiness. Most important thing for the security hardware engineers to consider in their design is to find the secrete channel for communication to lessen the complexity of the crypto algorithm used.

PS/2 Keyboard interface looks not designed considering security mentioned earlier. However, resource economy done on the PS/2 keyboard interface fortunately leads to possibility to find a easy way to distribute a secrete key and random vectors for keyboard data encryption.

Writing data into port 0x60 of the keyboard controller is a hidden and disposable action for dedicated software because the port is organized as a one way volatile interface in hardware. Because of the reason, the data written is bound only to the keyboard itself and never found in any other place and accessed except the dedicated software.

The number of possible keyboard scan codes is double of the number of possible key caps on the keyboard, which leads to not more than 256. This means that the scan code for one keycap is required to be changed in time randomly. One time key scheme is a good candidate for this requirement because it is easy for dedicated software and the keyboard to share the keys through the port 0x60.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION EXAMPLE

To utilize the method explained above, the keyboard should be re-programmed. It could be fine to incorporate security unction into keyboard itself. However, it is usually not acceptable because some people seldom want to replace their accustomed keyboard. A reasonable approach is to place a security hardware module between the host and the keyboard.

The security hardware module deals with the keyboard like as a normal host and implements a security function with the host security software. Figure 4 shows the internal function blocks implemented in the security hardware module including the connectors both to the host and the keyboard. Figure 5

shows the assembled security hardware module. The connector side of the module has a facility to reprogram the security function, which could be used when the security algorithm is exposed on the host side.

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 [6] Linda D. Paulson, Key "Snooping Technology Causes Controversy," IEEE Computer, pp.27, Mar. 2002.

Fig. 4 Internal function blocks of the security hardware module. It mainly consists of three different functions; the host-site processing, the keyboard-site processing and the security function. Security function needs just a simple randomized shared key cryptography because of the disposability of the PS/2 keyboard interface

Fig. 5 Implemented and reprogrammed security hardware for PS/2 keyboard as an example. USB keyboard is not considerable for a secure keyboard because the USB host controller has no disposable interface between the host and the target device and it is adapted to the PS/2 interface through a combo converter

V. CONCLUSION

This paper introduced a hardware based solution to the password sniff problem caused by the severe intrinsic hardware vulnerabilities of the keyboard hardware. Because the vulnerabilities still have no software based solution and even any possible candidates, it is required to have some types of reasonable hardware solutions. Fortunately the PS/2 keyboard interface on the host side has a disposable interface, only a simple shared key crypto algorithm is enough though it needs to have a one-time randomized key chain. However, because the USB interface is getting common for the keyboard, which is too weak for security applications, it is required to keep or deploy a disposable interface such as PS/2 in the PC platform or various new trials not using keyboard strings for passwords.[4]

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